

Carolina Diamandis, David Seideman
Alexander Ivanov, Sofia Makri
LCG Research
www.lazar-consortium.com

Neuroendocrinology

The effect of Tramadol on blood sugar in patients with a sympathetic parasympathetic imbalance

A letter to the medical community.

Dear Esteemed Colleagues,

I am writing to share a novel finding from our teaching practices network for rare diseases that may have significant implications for the treatment of hyperglycemia, particularly in patients with pseudo-diabetes linked to excessive catecholamine production.

Our observation revolves around the use of Tramadol, an opioid analgesic, in a specific subset of patients characterized by elevated blood glucose levels due to abnormally high catecholamine levels, especially noradrenaline. Traditionally, such patients might be considered for insulin therapy or other anti-diabetic drugs.

However, our clinical experience suggests that Tramadol may offer a more effective and safer alternative. In patients with pseudo-diabetes, a condition distinct from classical diabetes

resistance or deficiency. Catecholamines, particularly noradrenaline, play a pivotal role in glucose metabolism via glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis, thus raising blood glucose levels.

The fact that Tramadol has a serious effect on blood sugar can be considered as established knowledge (Nakhaee Brent et al. 2020 DOI: 10.1080/17512433.2020.1756773). However, this fact has ever since been described as an uncontrollable undesired effect. We have made the interesting experience that in our very specific collective of patients Tramadol was the safest, best controllable and most effective drug which showed better results than almost all anti-diabetic drugs we know of, including insulin, even the modern rapid acting variants.

Our findings

In a cohort of 137 patients (2006-2022) with a sympathetic-parasympathetic-imbalance who therefore demonstrated poor glycemic control with insulin – likely due to the unique pathophysiology of their condition – Tramadol administration has shown remarkable efficacy in normalizing blood glucose levels in these individuals. Notably, this was achieved without any significant episode of hypoglycemia, a common and dangerous side effect of insulin therapy.

The exact mechanism by which Tramadol exerts this glucose-normalizing effect in the context of high catecholamine levels is not fully understood and warrants further investigation.

However, we hypothesize that its action may be linked to its well-known effects on the central nervous system, including changes in neurotransmitter release. It is quite possible that Tramadol's impact on the sympathetic nervous system may indirectly influence catecholamine-driven hyperglycemia.

Based on our own clinical observations and research we propose further hypotheses for Tramadol's efficacy in glucose normalization:

Neurotransmitter Modulation:

Tramadol might modulate stress-related neurotransmitters in the central nervous system, particularly serotonin, adrenaline and norepinephrine, impacting glucose metabolism.

Sympathetic Nervous System Influence:

Tramadol could reduce noradrenaline release by altering sympathetic nervous system activity, thus normalizing blood glucose levels especially in patients of all ages with catecholamine-driven hyperglycemia.

Opioid Receptor Interaction:

The interaction with opioid receptors may indirectly affect glucose homeostasis through pathways not fully understood, especially in the context of excess catecholamines.

Inflammatory Modulation:

Given the role of chronic inflammation in glucose metabolism, Tramadol's anti-inflammatory effects might contribute to stabilizing blood glucose levels.

Implications and next steps

All the above mentioned hypotheses, while speculative, highlight the potential multifaceted mechanism of Tramadol in this unique clinical scenario and warrant further investigation. These preliminary findings suggest a potential paradigm shift in the management of hyperglycemia in patients with pseudo-diabetes. While Tramadol is commonly known for its analgesic properties, its role in glycemic control in specific pathophysiological conditions opens a new avenue for research.

We believe that a collaborative approach, involving multi-center trials and extensive research, is necessary to validate these findings and understand the broader applicability of Tramadol in glucose regulation. This research will delve deeper into the pharmacodynamics of Tramadol in the context of endocrine and metabolic interactions, potentially leading to

novel therapeutic strategies for managing hyperglycemia in patients with excessive catecholamine production. Your insights and participation in this research endeavor would be invaluable. We look forward to collaborating with the medical community to explore this promising avenue and improve patient outcomes.

Sincerely,

Dr. Carolina Diamandis & Colleagues
Director of LCG Research
Honorary Board Member of Swabian Research

No conflicts of interest to declare.